
**DESCRIPTION OF A NEW SPECIES FOR THE GENUS *CONUS*
(MOLLUSCA: GASTROPODA), FROM THE CAPE VERDE ISLANDS**

by
Herculano Trovão⁽¹⁾ and Emilio Rolán⁽²⁾

Introduction:

In the description of *Conus roeckeli* ROLÁN, 1980, several specimens were included in this taxon sharing small size, low spire, generally light colour with a variable pattern which under magnification consistently showed axial brown lines more or less broken by white spaces. Although at the occasion the presence of such specimens, with these characteristics and presenting minor differences in other aspects, had been noticed, they were considered as a geographical variation inhabiting Sal Rei Bay, as compared to the typical form, found in Gata Bay.

Deeper studies, completing the morphological observation of the shells with other anatomical features, especially concerning the structure of the radular tooth, have led to the conclusion that two distinct species were present, which had erroneously been mixed up and included under a single taxon.

The holotype of *C. roeckeli*, housed in the Museo de Ciencias Naturales de Madrid, shows the typical pattern of its species. But it so happened that the radular tooth presented in the original description does not belong to the holotype, but indeed to another specimen, kept as a paratype. For this reason and in order to reach definitive conclusions, the authors made a thorough revision of the type material of *C. roeckeli* and of large samples from different locations, so as to set their reasoning on objective data and avoid personal intuition. One of the main pieces of evidence for the separation of the two species was undoubtedly the comparison of radular teeth characteristics.

Drawings of radular teeth from different *Conus* species have been published irregularly since long ago (BERGH, 1895; PEILE, 1939; ENDEAN & RUDKIN, 1965; WARMKE, 1960; NYBAKKEN, 1970), showing the differences between one another. In the reviewed bibliography for the genus, there are several works in which the radula plays the leading role in the separation of species (VAN MOL, TURSCH & KEMPF, 1971; TROVÃO, 1975, 1975a, 1978, 1978a, 1979; BANDEL & WILS, 1977; MCLEAN & NYBAKKEN, 1979; NYBAKKEN & JAMES, 1980). In such works, differences in the morphology of radular teeth are usually matched by other morphological differences.

At the present moment, however, there is still no published paper establishing beyond reasonable doubt the constancy of radular characteristics and their importance in specific separation. Work is being done on this project and even if it is too long to be extensively mentioned here, we can bring forward some of the conclusions obtained so far:

(1) Laboratório de Malacologia, C.P.A.S., R. Alto do Duque 45, 1400 Lisboa, Portugal.

(2) Cánovas del Castillo, 22-5.º F, Vigo 2, España.

The study of the radular teeth of two species gives us more differential elements for comparison than the study of shells. Carefully chosen radular features are specifically constant and hence suitable as data for species diagnosis and separation.

So, the study of the constant elements of the radular tooth of a given species has a much value for the separation of species as other features such as shell shape and coloration, egg capsules and protoconch structure.

VAN MOL, TURSCH and KEMPF (1971) have already highlighted the usefulness of radulae for the study of variable species, where the observation of shell characteristics may eventually lead to wrong conclusions.

When it comes to the protoconch, a perfect observation is usually impossible for Cape Verde species, since the spires are very often covered with heavy calcareous incrustations.

When examining a large number of specimens so far grouped under the single taxon *C. roeckeli*, two morphologically separable groups could be recognized: the first one, agreeing with the holotype and paratypes 1, 2 and 3, as well as with other specimens from Gata Bay, Boavista Island, showed well marked shoulders, white sutures, dark reddish or black living animals and were always found under rocks in 3 to 5 meters water; the second group included specimens coming from Sal Rei Bay, taken in shallow water, on algae and presenting a more rounded shoulder, light pink living animal and highly variable shell pattern. The radular study of large samples of specimens from these two groups yielded two distinct radular patterns, clearly and consistently different.

For all these reasons and because of the constancy in different features in both shell and radular morphology, we have reached the conclusion that two distinct species were being so far treated as one. We thus propose the following new taxon:

Conus diminutus sp. n.

(Fig. 3 A, B, C)

Description:

Shell small, obconical, the last whorl almost straight sided. Although apparently smooth and shiny, the shell surface is really finely striated, with some grooves at the basis. The shell is white or light cream, sometimes faintly bluish, and has a pattern of fine light brown axially undulating lines which by coming together form dark brownish spots, very irregular as to colour and size. These spots usually form three dark brown bands, one near the shoulder, another shortly above mid-body and a third one on the anterior zone; the brown spots can even form large areas which occupy most of the shell surface; they can rarely be very sparse.

The lip has a slightly curved profile, the interior being whitish but with three pink or light violet areas spreading towards the interior of the shell; these areas can also be brownish and are separated by two white lines, one near the sinus and the other at about mid-length.

The spire is low with a straight profile, sometimes slightly convex. Spire whorls present 3 to 4 axial striae.

The protoconch is slightly coloured, although eroded in most specimens. The columella is dark.

There is no sexual dimorphism. The penis is readily seen in 6.5 mm specimens and is slender, thinning and curving towards the tip and presenting a circular section.

The periostracum is fine, yellow, transparent and not hairy. The operculum is ovoid or elongated and very variable.

The living animal presents a cream colour on the underside and the lateral zone of the foot; it varies from whitish to pinkish, rarely reddish. Quite abundant white points show through, while at the surface there is a grayish pigmentation forming isolated spots which are more abundant on the upper side of the foot and in its borders and also towards the head and siphon, which can be of a dark shade.

Dimensions:

624 specimens have been studied, from the collections of both authors, C.P.A.S., FRANCISCO FERNANDES, DIETER RÖCKEL, JOÃO MESSIAS, ANTÔNIO MONTEIRO, IGNACIO NAVARRO, MIRUCHA GARRIDO, AMARÍLIO RAMALHO, CÉSAR FERNANDES, GUILHERME SOARES and JOSÉ BORGES, and also some material from the first Iberic Expedition to the Cape Verde Islands.

Most specimens coming from Sal Rei were smaller than 10 mm. Measurements taken from material from the mentioned expedition, which took place in 1985, showed that only 10 shells were larger than 13 mm; 17 measured more than 10 mm, while 105 were smaller. Nevertheless, we saw specimens from other areas which reached larger sizes, as the ones FERNANDES and MESSIAS collected on the outer coast of Ilhéu de Sal Rei.

Types:

The holotype, which belonged to the collection of Emilio Rolán measures 11,1 mm by 6,5 mm and is deposited in the Museo de Ciencias Naturales de Madrid.

Paratypes are housed in several collections, listed in Table 1.

Egg Capsules:

The egg capsules are 2 to 3 mm high, globose, thinning a little towards the top and presenting, all over their surface, rounded or ovoid cavities, quite irregular, absent only from the upper opening, which presents inconspicuous wings reaching half the length of the capsule. Inside each capsule, 4 or 5 eggs are found; the juvenile, when ready to leave the capsule, is yellow all over, with only two dashes of colour on the free edge.

C. diminutus n. sp.: egg capsules (2 mm)

Radula:

The radular sac presents a number of teeth somewhat higher than in other endemic species (47 to 67 for the new taxon, against 35 to 50 for most others). The teeth are quite wide and comparatively large in relation to shell length; radular tooth/shell length ratio varies from 32 to 43. The upper zone of the tooth is proportionally small (from apex to waist), its ratio to the total length varying from 2.64 to 2.93 (these figures refer to 20 studied specimens and more than 500 measured teeth).

The anterior barb is not very conspicuous and is slightly laterally placed. The serration is narrow, with 8 to 18 denticles (according to the size of the animal), placed in a single line. The posterior edge of the serration is slightly undulated. The union of the serration's basis with the posterior edge of the tooth forms an angle of about 45.° The anterior edge has a clearly visible blade, which always ends shortly above the waist. Wider posterior end and strong basis, with a spur.

Discussion:

Since the present species shows a variable pattern, it can at first sight resemble other endemic species: the closest one (to the point of being grouped with the new taxon, as explained above) is *Conus roeckeli*, which however presents a lighter spire with isolated spots, always a white sutural edge, more angulous shoulder, white columella, spiral grooves often numbering three and well marked and the axial coloured lines are more interrupted by large white areas. The radular tooth is somewhat larger but much thinner; the ratio between its total length and the length of the anterior zone is 2.2 to 2.3. The serration is much wider, with many more denticles which, towards the bottom, may form 3 rows. The anterior blade is not very pronounced and extends to the waist.

Some specimens of the present species which show few dots and a dark spire can resemble *C. salreiensis* ROLÁN, 1980, but this has larger and more separated axial lines which are also more regular; the ground colour is more uniform and the inside of the aperture is usually lighter. The radular tooth always has a longer anterior zone (only a little less than the total length), it is narrower, the angle at the end of the serration is smaller and the number of denticles in the serration is higher; the radular tooth has a more pronounced lateral curvature.

Young specimens of *C. borgesii* TROVÃO, 1979 could also look alike, but they are wider, the spire profile is somewhat concave, the suture is white, the protoconch is coloured, the interior is white and the pattern is distinct.

In some specimens, the adjoining of the axial lines may create a pattern resembling that of *C. verdensis* TROVÃO, 1979, but this species never presents fine lines in its pattern, the spire is always dark while the columella is constantly white. The egg capsule is completely different.

C. diminutus n. sp.: penis

The almost constant presence of axial lines separates it from most other endemic species, with the exception of the populations provisionally included in the taxon *C. cuneolus* REEVE, 1844, found in Fontona and Rigona Bays, but both show a quite constant and distinct pattern, a considerably larger size and on the other hand the tips of their protoconches are always dark and the columella white.

Specimens without axial lines and with white spots may resemble juvenile specimens of *C. cuneolus* and *C. delanoyi* TROVÃO, 1979, but both are darker and have a well marked shoulder; their radular teeth are different, with an anterior zone equal to or longer than half the total length.

The orientation of the axial lines also separates it at once from *C. damottai* TROVÃO, 1979.

No other species are close enough to cause any confusion.

Habitat:

Most specimens found were among small algae, on rocks in very shallow water, very near high tide level; occasionally under rocks, down to 1 m deep.

RESUMEN

Se describe una nueva especie del género *Conus* perteneciente a la fauna endémica de Cabo Verde, la cual anteriormente había sido confundida con otra especie, mostrándose también las diferencias con otras especies del género. El holotipo queda depositado en el Museo de Ciencias Naturales de Madrid.

SUMMARY

We describe a new species of the genus *Conus* from Cape Verde's endemic fauna, showing the differences to another one which has been considered as the same species, as well as to other species of the same genus. The holotype is deposited in the Museo de Ciencias Naturales of Madrid.

RESUMO

Descreve-se uma nova espécie do género *Conus*, pertencente à fauna endémica do Arquipélago de Cabo Verde, separada de outra com a qual, anteriormente, tinha sido confundida, mostrando-se também as diferenças existentes em relação a outras espécies do mesmo género. O holotipo fica depositado no Museo de Ciencias Naturales, de Madrid.

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C. diminutus n. sp.: pattern variation

A

B

C

A, B — *C. diminutus n. sp.*: holotype
C — *C. diminutus n. sp.*: colour variation

Figura

- A — Protoconch from *C. diminutus sp. n.* × 100
- B — Juvenile from *C. diminutus sp. n.* × 85
- C — Microsculpture from protoconch × 250
- D — Radular tooth from *C. diminutus sp. n.* (paratype) 15,8 mm.
- E — Radular tooth from *C. roeckeli* Rolan, 1980 (paratype) 15 mm.